

Elimination of organophosphate pesticides from fruits using chemical neutralizer: pesticides denatured from *Vitis vinifera* (Grapes) using BTEAC.

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ABSTRACT

Organophosphate (OP) pesticides, as a group, are most widely used insecticides in India. OP pesticides are generally used on fruits, vegetables, grains, and pasture seed, cotton, on livestock and domestic animals as well as for building pest control. Pesticides compounds represent an important class of pollutants for food, soil and surface water resources. These pesticides remain in the fruits and vegetables and cannot be removed even after washing which is very harmful and affects the human health, so to remove or neutralize these harmful pesticides the chemical neutralizer solution Benzyltriethyl ammonium chloride 50% was prepared. The main objective of this chemical neutralizer is to eliminate the organophosphate pesticides from fruits. The suitable method was used to eliminate or neutralize the organophosphate pesticides from fruits. Four pesticides were used namely chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, Malathion and monocrotophos. These pesticides were applied on grapes. Benzyltriethyl ammonium chloride helps in denaturation of organophosphate pesticide and hence it was used as a chemical neutralizer for neutralizing the pesticides present on the fruits. The Benzyltriethyl ammonium chloride was diluted with distilled water and concentration was made to 50%. Different concentrations of Benzyltriethyl ammonium chloride were also used for neutralization, but 50% concentration was best and didn't affect the fruits. After organophosphate pesticides were applied, then the samples were kept in chemical neutralizer for an hour which neutralizes residual agricultural pesticide, then the samples underwent distilled water wash to remove neutralizer contents. The samples were tested for pesticide detection using gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GCMS). The results obtained were very positive and effective. The contents of pesticide were neutralized up to 80% in contrast with that of the contents of only pesticides. This solution is a noncorrosive, nontoxic, nonflammable decontaminant, which is used to neutralize organophosphate pesticides from fruits. This chemical is useful on all fruits containing organophosphorus pesticides.

KEYWORDS: Pesticides, Fruits, BTEAC, Organophosphate, Malathion, Dimethoate, Chlorpyrifos, Monocrotophos.

INTRODUCTION

Pesticides are chemical substances used to kill insects and animals that destroy crops. They are

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characterized by pronounced persistence against chemical/biological degradation, high environmental mobility, strong tendency for bioaccumulation in human and animal tissues, and significant impacts on human health and the environment, even at extremely low concentrations (H. Liu et al., 2009). India is a predominantly agrarian country with about 60-80% rural population. Pesticides are routinely used for advanced farming. These are readily available over the counter. Therefore, a pesticide is an easy access source for suicidal purpose particularly after trivial family squabbles. Such little petty quarrels often that result in consumption of pesticide for suicide purpose is a matter of routine

news in local dailies. Poisoning is seldom included as a priority for health research in India, though every year, hundreds of people are losing their lives prematurely from pesticide poisoning (HS Bawasker et al., 2005). Classification of pesticides is as per their acute toxicity, as classified by the World Health Organization. This classification includes Class Ia – Extremely hazardous, demarcated in red; Class Ib – Highly Hazardous, symbolized by a yellow triangle; Class II – Moderately Hazardous, marked by a blue triangle. Class III is known as “Slightly Hazardous” while the remaining class is supposed to be “Not likely to be Hazardous”. It is to be noted here that two-thirds of the pesticides consumed here fall under WHO Class I and II pesticides. From 1998 to 2005, the decline in Class Ia pesticides has been only 2% - from 11% to 9% (K Kuruganti et al., 2007).

Figure 1. Depicts the different toxicity levels of pesticides

Material and Methods

Following Organophosphate Pesticides were employed:

1. Chlorpyrifos 20% EC
2. Malathion 50% EC
3. Dimethoate 30% EC
4. Monocrotophos 36% EC

The above mentioned pesticides were purchased from Namdeo Umaji Agritech (India) Pvt. Ltd, Byculla.

Following compound was used:

Benzyltriethyl Ammonium Chloride pure (BTEAC). This compound was purchased from SRL.

Figure 2. Depicts the structure of BTEAC

Fruits used in this study: Grapes (*Vitis vinifera*)

110%Solution Preparation:

The compound BTEAC was taken as a pure form and 11grams was weighed on the weighing machine. Then 10ml of distilled water was taken in the beaker.

To the 10ml distilled water, 11gram of BTEAC was added and was mixed by shaking gently.

Treatment of BTEAC solution 110% concentration on Grapes:

Fresh grapes were taken from the market and were placed on the Petri plate. To the grapes the BTEAC – 110% concentrated solution was sprayed with the help of sprayer. Then the grapes were kept for observation.

BTEAC 50%Solution Preparation:

The compound BTEAC was taken as a pure form. About 5gram was weighed on the weighing machine. Then 10ml of distilled water was taken in the beaker. To the 10ml distilled water 5gm of BTEAC was added and was mixed by shaking gently.

Treatment of BTEAC solution 50% concentration on Grapes:

Fresh grapes were taken from the market and were put on Petri plate. To the grapes the BTEAC – 50% concentrated solution was sprayed with the help of sprayer. Then again the grapes were kept for observation.

Sample Preparation for GCMS:

Four organophosphorus pesticide namely chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, Malathion and monocrotophos were taken. The grapes were first sprayed with chlorpyrifos, then they were air dried. Then they were sprayed with dimethoate and kept for air drying. Again they were sprayed with monocrotophos and Malathion and again grapes were air dried. Before application of each pesticide the grapes were air dried. After drying the grapes were dipped in BTEAC 50% concentration and few of them were dipped in the beaker containing distilled water which was taken as a blank. The grapes were kept for about an hour in BTEAC 50% concentration and distilled water. After one hour the grapes were removed and kept for drying. The grapes removed from BTEAC 50% concentration were washed with the distilled water (Figure 5). These grapes after drying were given for GCMS for detection of pesticide residue (Figure 3). GCMS was performed at Microchem Silliker, Mahape, Navi Mumbai (Figure 13, Figure 14, Figure 15, Figure 16).

The samples of grapes were prepared for GCMS testing:

Sample 1 – Pesticides were sprayed on the grapes and then the grapes were dipped into the chemical neutralizer BTEAC 50% (50g in 10ml of distilled water) and then washed with the distilled water.

Sample 2 – Pesticides were sprayed on the grapes and then the grapes were dipped into the distilled water.

Figure 3. Depicts the step by step procedure.

Results

The effect of BTEAC 110% concentration on grapes:

The Grapes were tested with different concentrations of pesticides and chemical neutralizer on it. The neutralizer (BTEAC) was made with 110% concentration and sprayed on Grapes. Control was

also made on which nothing was sprayed. This was Day 1.

Sample 1 – Control nothing was sprayed on Grapes.

Sample 2 – Chemical neutralizer BTMAC 110% concentration (11g in 10ml distill water) was sprayed on Grapes.

Figure 4. (Left) beaker containing distilled water (control) and (right) beaker containing BTEAC 50% (test).

Figure 5. (Left) Grapes dipped in distilled water (control) and (right) Grapes dipped in the BTEAC 50% solution (test).

Figure 6. On day 4, Grapes showed abnormal secretion around them and shrinkage was observed possibly due to high concentration of BTEAC (110%).

Effect of BTEAC 50% concentration on grapes:

Three samples of grapes were prepared

- a) Sample 1 – Control
- b) Sample 2 - 50% chemical neutralizer BTEAC (i.e. 5g in 10ml distilled water) was sprayed on grapes and then washed with distilled water.
- c) Sample 3 – 50% chemical neutralizer BTEAC (i.e. 5g in 10ml distilled water) was sprayed on grapes

Figure 7. Sample 3 of grapes showed abnormal secretion around it on day 1 due to BTEAC 50%.

Figure 8. Grapes samples 1 and 2 remained normal whereas sample 3 continued to show secretion on day 2 and day 3.

Figure 9. Grapes sample 3 were showing abnormal cavities and dark spots but sample 1 (Control) and sample 2 treated with BTEAC and distilled water remained normal on day 4 and 5.

Effect of Organophosphates on Grapes:

On Grapes four organophosphate pesticides were sprayed and kept under observation for a week.

Figure 10. Grapes sprayed with 4 different pesticides under observation, no changes occurred on day 1.

Figure 11. Grapes with pesticides showing no signs of damage on day 2 and 3.

Figure 12. Grapes with pesticide showed abnormality in shape and started to shrink on day 6 and 7

Results of GCMS:

Results of GCMS performed at Microchem Silliker, Mahape, Navi Mumbai

Description of the Graph and the table:

Without neutralizer the contents of the different pesticides are Chlorpyrifos 10mg/kg, Dimethoate 0.90mg/kg, Monocrotophos 0.40mg/kg, and Malathion 0.53mg/kg. After using neutralizers these reduces as Chlorpyrifos 2mg/kg, Dimethoate 0.80mg/kg, Monocrotophos 0.29mg/kg, and Malathion 0.11mg/kg. The OPs are denatured and neutralized with chemical neutralizer BTEAC solution. In these experiments the chlorpyrifos which has class II toxicity level gets neutralized up to 80% which is a very good result. The Malathion which has class II toxicity level also gets neutralized up to 80%.

The monocrotophos which has class Ib toxicity level also gets neutralized up to 12.5%. The dimethoate which has class II toxicity level gets neutralized up to 30%. These all results are very effective and help in neutralization of all the Ops ([Table 1](#)) and ([Graph-1](#)).

Effect of BTEAC 110% concentration on Grapes:

As per the treatment of BTEAC 110% concentration on grapes described in the methods section, the grapes were normal on day 1 but on day 4 the control showed shrinkage whereas the grapes on which BTEAC 110% concentration was applied showed abnormal secretion and abnormal cavities. Henceforth, it was concluded from the result that the grapes were not able to bear high concentration of BTEAC solution on it. The result is shown ([Figure-6](#)).

Effect of BTEAC solution 50% concentration on Grapes:

As per the treatment of BTEAC solution 50% concentration on grapes described in the methods section, the sample 1 and sample 2 were normal whereas sample 3 had abnormal secretion as shown ([Figure-7](#)) Till day 3 there were abnormal secretion in sample 3 whereas there were no changes in sample 1 and sample 2 ([Figure-9](#)). Sample 1 was control and sample 2 was treated with BTEAC solution 50% concentration and after treatment it was washed with distilled water to remove the chemical neutralizer BTEAC solution 50% concentration.

.Effect of Water Wash:

After the treatment of pesticide and chemical neutralizer on grapes the grapes are dried and then the grapes are washed with distilled water to remove or wash away the chemical neutralizer present on the fruits. These wash removes all contents of the chemical neutralizer BTEAC solution and therefore there is no other effects on grapes/fruits and good for consumption.

Discussions

The benefits of pesticides include increased food production, increased profits for farmers and the prevention of diseases. Although pests consume or harm a large portion of agricultural crops, without the use of pesticides, it is likely that they would consume a higher percentage. The Registration Committee (RC) registers pesticides for their usage, their MRL in food and commodities are prescribed by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare under PFA (Act), 1954 and rules framed thereunder. What is alarming to note is that in India, MRL as a concept is being wrongly formulated while implementation status is worse. While pesticides are registered without MRLs being necessarily fixed before or during registration, there are no enforcement mechanisms available to ensure liability for violation of MRLs at least by the organized food industry. During evidence to the Joint Parliamentary Committee formed in 2004, representative of the Ministry of Agriculture and the

Figure 13. Scanned Test results obtained for the Grapes with pesticides and distilled water wash, Microchem Silliker, page 1 (report no. 151602001).

TEST REPORT	
REPORT NO.: 151602001	REPORT DATE : 13/04/2015
Customer Name	Anuj Thapar
Address	804, Marathon Galaxy II, LBS Marg, Mulund(W), Mumbai, Maharashtra-400080
Contact Person	Mr. Anuj Thapar
Sample(s) Drawn by The Laboratory	No
Date of Sample Received	06/04/2015
Date of Starting Analysis	08/04/2015
Date of Completion	10/04/2015
Sample Description	Grapes With Pesticide
Sample Details	Nature: Fruit, Ref : Veg/Raw, Qty : 118gms, Stamped/Sealed : No, Packing : Plastic Container

PARAMETER NAME	RESULT	UOM	METHOD
Acephate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorfenvinphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorpyrifos	10.0	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorpyrifos methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Dimethoate	0.90	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Diazinon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Dichlorvos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Ethion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Etrimphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Fenitrothion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Iprobenphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Malathion	0.53	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Methamidophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Monocrotophos	0.40	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Omethoate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Oxydemeton-Methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phosphamidon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Parathion-Ethyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Parathion-Methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phosalone	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phorate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Profenophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Quinolophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
4-Bromo-2-Chlorophenol	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Triazophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34

151602001

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262880

Figure 14. Scanned Test results obtained for the Grapes with pesticides and distilled water wash, Microchem Silliker, page 2 (report no. 151602001).

TEST REPORT

REPORT NO.: 151602001 REPORT DATE: 13/04/2015

Remark : BLQ : Below Limit of Quantification, Quantification Limit for pesticides: 0.01 mg/kg

..... END

Suhasee
Authorized Signatory

Note: 1. Test results relate to the submitted sample(s) only. 2. Test report shall not be reproduced except in full, without written approval of the laboratory. 3. Laboratory is not responsible for the authenticity of photocopied test report. 4. The test items will not be retained for perishable products and 1 months in the case of non-perishable samples unless otherwise agreed with the customer or as required by the applicable regulation. 5. The tests marked with (*) are not accredited by NABL.

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Figure 14. Scanned Test results obtained for Grapes with pesticides, neutralizer wash and distilled water wash, Microchem Silliker, page 1 (report no. 151601999).

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TEST REPORT			
REPORT NO.: 151601999		REPORT DATE: 13/04/2015	
Customer Name	Anuj Thapar		
Address	804, Marathon Galaxy II, LBS Marg, Mulund(W), Mumbai, Maharashtra-400080		
Contact Person	Mr. Anuj Thapar		
Sample(s) Drawn by The Laboratory	No		
Date of Sample Received	06/04/2015		
Date of Starting Analysis	08/04/2015		
Date of Completion	10/04/2015		
Sample Description	Grapes With Neutralizer & Pesticide		
Sample Details	Nature: Fruit, Ref : Veg/Raw, Qty : 143gms, Stamped/Sealed : No, Packing : Plastic Container		

PARAMETER NAME	RESULT	UOM	METHOD
Acephate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorfenvinphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorpyrifos	2	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorpyrifos methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Dimethoate	0.80	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Diazinon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Dichlorvos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Ethion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Etrimphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Fenitrothion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Iprobenphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Malathion	0.11	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Methamidophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Monocrotophos	0.29	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Omethoate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Oxydemeton-Methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phosphamidon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Parathion-Ethyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Parathion-Methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phosalone	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phorate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Profenophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Quinolphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
4-Bromo-2-Chlorophenol	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Triazophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34

151601999

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Figure 16. Scanned Test results obtained for Grapes with pesticides, neutralizer wash and distilled water wash, Microchem Silliker, page 2 (report no. 151605169).

TEST REPORT

REPORT NO.: 151601999 REPORT DATE: 13/04/2015

Remark : BLQ : Below Limit of Quantification, Quantification Limit for pesticides : 0.01 mg/kg

..... **END**

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Table 1. Indicates presence of different pesticides in grapes with and without chemical neutralizer

Test for Grapes		
Name of the Pesticides	Without neutralizers contents of the Pesticides (mg/kg)	With neutralizers contents of the Pesticides (mg/kg)
	Chlorpyrifos	10.0
Dimethoate	0.90	0.80
Monocrotophos	0.40	0.29
Malathion	0.53	0.11

Director General of Health Services admitted that out of 181 pesticides registered at that time, tolerance limits (MRLs) have been fixed for only 71 pesticides. For another 50 pesticides, such tolerance limits were in the process of finalization. It has been concluded that there are about 27 pesticides registered in the country which do not require fixation of tolerance limits. This means 32 pesticides which are still left for tolerance limits to be fixed – for eight of these, it was decided to follow Codex norms for the time being since data was not available and was being collected. Data for 24 pesticides where are “deemed-to-be-registered” has been submitted. As part of this study, an interesting exercise was taken up, to compare the data between registration recommendation for each pesticide and the recommendations of agriculture departments and finally, the recommendations by the company’s manufacturing and selling the pesticides. For example, Acephate is registered for use only on Cotton and Safflower in the country. It is not registered for use on Chillies, Brinjal, Cabbage,

Cauliflower, Apple, Castor, Mango, Tomato, Potato, Grapes, Okra, Onion, Mustard, Paddy and many other crops where it is being used extensively now. Further, it is also being recommended by the NARS for use in other crops even without registration! Acephate is being recommended for the control of sap sucking pests in most crops. Further, MRLs have been set only for safflower seed and cotton seed for this pesticide. Survey report conducted by Indian agricultural research institute indicates that a total of 4239 vegetable samples of brinjal, okra, tomato, cabbage, capsicum and cauliflower, collected from various wholesale/retail markets located at different parts of the country were analysed during April 2009-March 2010 by 17 participating laboratories. The pesticide residues were detected in 417 samples out of which 137 samples were found to contain residues of more than one pesticide. Residues detected in most of the samples were below the MRL. In 84 samples the residues were found above MRL levels. The maximum number of detectable samples have been reported by P.C.Cell, New Delhi (225 Samples) followed by IITR, Lucknow (69 samples); PAU, Ludhiana (35 samples); IIHR, Bangalore (30 samples) and AAU nAnand (29 samples) laboratories. The pesticides mainly reported by P.C.Cell are chlorpyrifos (59 samples) and endosulfan (69 samples). The most predominantly detected pesticides in vegetable sample by different centres are chlorpyrifos (122 samples), endosulfan (110 samples), profenophos (55 samples) and triazophos (41 samples). Of the various vegetable samples analyzed, highest numbers of pesticides were detected in Okra (184 samples) out of which 11 samples contained residues of chlorpyrifos, cypermetgrin and monocrotophos above MRL. The

Graph 1. Graphical representation of the results obtained from the GCMS test for grapes.

second highest number of detectable residues were found in tomato samples (110 samples) viz., cauliflower, brinjal and cabbage showed the presence of pesticide residues in 56, 90 and 40 samples, respectively (Anuj Thapar et al., 2015).

Conclusion

The presence of pesticide residues is a concern for consumers because organophosphates are known to have potential harmful effects to other non-targeted organisms than pests and diseases. People have environmental exposures to pesticides mainly through diet. Human intake due to pesticide residues in food commodities is usually much higher than those related to water consumption and air. The evaluation of pesticide residues in food is nowadays a priority objective to ensure food quality and to protect consumers against possible health risks. Fruits and vegetables are important components of the human diet since they provide essential nutrients that are required for most of the reactions occurring in the body (Aman Zalawadia et al., 2015). A high intake of fruits and vegetables (five or more servings per day) has been encouraged not only to prevent consequences due to vitamin deficiency but also to reduce the incidence of major diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases and obesity. Contamination of fruits and vegetables may result from treatment as well as from conditions such as improper or overuse of pesticides, residues from preceding treatments in the soil and cross contamination (particularly during harvesting). Due to their high solubility in water, organophosphates are distributed in aqueous food such as fruits and related derivatives. These can be dangerous if consumed. In this study, Efforts were made to eliminate the pesticides that were sprayed on the Grapes. The results were Fascinating. The contents of pesticide were neutralized up to 80% in contrast with that of the contents of only pesticides. The solution which was prepared is noncorrosive, nontoxic, nonflammable decontaminant, which can be used to neutralize organophosphate pesticides from Fruits. This chemical is effective on all fruits containing organophosphorus pesticides.

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Conflict of Interests:

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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